

TABLE 1—PHYSICAL PROPERTIES AND ANALYTICAL DATA OF NAPHTHYLCHALCONES

R'	R	Yield %	Colour & crystals	M. P. °C of		Halochromism with Conc. H ₂ SO ₄	Analyses
				Chal.	2:4-DNP		
4'-OH	H ^f	63	Yellow rods	191	—	Red	C,H
4'-OH	2-Cl	78	Violet prisms	217	249	Dark Red	C,H,N
4'-OH	3-Cl	62	Shining rods	156	227d	Red	C,H,N
4'-OH	4-Cl	76	L. Y. rods	194	263	Blood red	C,H,N
4'-OH	2-Me	54	Y. Plates	196	221d	Brown	C,H,N
4'-OH	3-Me	60	Y. rods	157	251f	Red	C,H,N
4'-OH	4-Me ^a	63	C.Y. needles	177	241	Dark red	C,H,N
4'-OH	2-NO ₂	68	Y. Plates	214	—	Brown	C,H
4'-OH	3-NO ₂	62	L. Y. Plates	190	—	Bloodred	C,H
4'-OH	4-NO ₂	78	Ochre Plates	181	—	Greenish Y.	C,H
4'-OH-3'-NO ₂	5-Br-2-OH	61	Y. needles	159	—	Greenish	C,H
4'-OH-3'-NO ₂	2-CH ₃	54	Tiny needles	94	211	Blood red	C,H,N
4'-OH-3'-NO ₂	5-Br-3, 4-(OCH ₃) ₂	57	Y. Globules	146	—	Pink	C,H,N
4'-OH-3'-NO ₂	5:6-Benzo	51	Brown Needles	153	—	Dirty Yellow	C,H

* All melting points are uncorrected since they were recorded in open capillary.
Crystallised from : a= dioxan ; f= Benzene
C.=Canary, L.=Lemon, Y.=Yellow

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Studies in some β -Ketoester Complexes

UMA DORASWAMY and P. K. BHATTACHARYA

Chemistry Department, Faculty of Science,
M. S. University, Baroda-2

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THE study of binary metal β -diketone complexes have been carried out earlier.^{1,2} It is known that in β -diketone complexes there is metal ligand π -interaction and formation of a six membered planar ring with-

delocalised π -electrons.³⁻⁵ In the metal chelates of benzoylacetone and dibenzoylmethane the delocalised π -electron cloud over the phenyl rings enhances the resonance effect, resulting in more stable complexes⁶.

In case of β -ketoesters, however, the metal ligand formation constant values are lowered considerably, as compared to the diketones and this has been attributed to the fact that the resonance in the chelate ring of the diketone is greatly interfered due to the participation of one of the carbonyl groups in the very strong ester resonance⁷.

The studies of the complexes of acetoacetic esters with substitution at the third carbon atom have not been carried out earlier. In the present investigation studies of binary metal β -ketoester complexes have been carried out by using Irving-Rossotti method⁸, and the metal ions used are Cu (II), Ni (II), Zn (II) and Be (II). The ligands are ethylacetoacetate, ethyl-2-methylacetoacetate, ethyl-2-ethylacetoacetate, ethyl-2-propylacetoacetate, ethyl-2-isopropyl acetoacetate, ethyl-2-butyl acetoacetate.

In case of acetoacetic ester and the C-alkyl acetoacetic ester, the steric hindrance of C-alkyl with-OC₂H₅ group is expected to be more than in case of acetylacetone. Thus the difference in the proton ligand and metal ligand formation constant values in case of acetoacetic ester and C-alkyl derivatives should be more than in acetylacetone and C-alkyl acetylacetone. However, the difference is less in case of β -ketoesters. This is because in case of β -ketoesters the enol form is already very much reduced and hence lowering in the enol form due to ring distortion does not have significant effect.

The smaller difference in the values of M-L formation constants of acetoacetic ester and C-substituted derivatives also shows that the distortion in planarity has small difference on the values of metal ligand formation constants. This indicates low resonance stabilisation of chelate ring in β -ketoesters than in β -diketone complexes.

TABLE 1—PROTON AND METAL LIGAND STABILITY CONSTANTS OF β -KETOESTERS AT 30°

Ligand	P H		Cu(II)		Ni(II)		Zn(II)		Be(II)	
	K ₁	K ₂								
1. Ethylacetoacetate	11.11	8.80	7.45	6.60	6.37	6.43	6.10	6.03	—	—
2. Ethyl-2-methylacetoacetate	11.25	8.70	7.40	6.57	6.25	6.38	6.00	5.95	—	—
3. Ethyl-2-ethylacetoacetate	11.29	8.69	7.39	6.48	6.10	6.16	5.83	5.87	—	—
4. Ethyl-2-propylacetoacetate	11.37	8.57	7.32	5.96	5.76	5.90	5.57	—	—	—
5. Ethyl-2-isopropylacetoacetate	11.38	8.60	7.39	6.00	5.83	5.95	5.70	—	—	—
6. Ethyl-2-butylacetoacetate	11.49	8.40	7.15	5.90	5.73	5.82	5.42	—	—	—

Experimental

The reagents used were all of pure grade. In order to avoid the complexing tendency of the anion, metal perchlorates were prepared and their metal contents determined. Dioxan was purified and sodium hydroxide was made free from carbonate by the methods suggested by Vogel^{9,10}. The instruments used and the titrations carried out are similar as in earlier publications¹¹. In each case of titration the volume was so adjusted that each solution was 50% dioxan by volume and the ionic strength was 0.2M. The solutions were titrated against 0.2M sodium hydroxide. In each case the pH values were corrected for the dioxan solution, using the method adopted by Van Viter and Haas¹². The values of logK₁ and logK₂ were computed by the method of least square^{13,14}.

Results and Discussion

The proton ligand and metal ligand stability constants of the above mentioned β -ketoester are shown in the Table. A small increase in the basicity of the substituted acetoacetic ester is noted than in the acetoacetic ester and this may be attributed mainly to the inductive effect of the alkyl groups.

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